

Interaction of Nickel-, Cobalt-, Zinc- and Lead(II) with Benzothiazole-2-carboxyhydrazides in Solution : Synthesis of their Copper(II) Complexes

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The Cu^{II} complexes of benzothiazole-2-carboxyhydrazide (BTCH), benzothiazole-2-(1'-N-methyl)carboxyhydrazide (BTCMH) and benzothiazole-2-(1'-N-phenyl)carboxyhydrazide (BTCPH) have been synthesized. Proton-ligand constants of BTCH, BTCPH and BTCMH and metal-ligand formation constants of their binary complexes with Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} have been determined in 70% (v/v) DMF-water medium at 303 K and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength. The formation constants follow the order : log K₁ > log K₂ for all the complexes. The stability order with respect to ligands follows the sequence : M(II)-BTCMH > M(II)-BTCH > M(II)-BTCPH.

Benzothiazole-2-carboxyhydrazides have interesting ligational properties due to the presence of several potential coordinating sites. Arif *et al.*¹ studied the Fe^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of 2-methylbenzothiazole and revealed nitrogen as coordination site. Arun and Ram² synthesized the Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of terdentate dibasic O,N,O donor Schiff bases derived from 2-benzothiazolecarboxyhydrazide. In general, ionization of carboxyhydrazides occurs at high pH and hence complexes are formed without replacing H⁺ ion from amide group³. In the present study, an attempt has been made to understand the coordination sites of BTCH, BTCPH and BTCMH by potentiometric studies in 70% (v/v) DMF-water medium. The Cu^{II} complexes with the same ligands have been synthesized.

Results and Discussion

Equilibrium studies : From potentiometric titrations, it has been observed that there is one dissociable proton present in BTCH. In general, the amide proton in hydrazides is highly basic. The pK_a at 10.45 indicates ionization of proton below pH 14 which is due to the presence of electron-withdrawing benzothiazole group. Now whether the deprotonation is taking place from N when the ligand is in keto form or from the oxygen when the ligand is in enol form, is a pertinent question. It is established that the peptide link is rigid with no freedom of rotation about the C=N bond. This is due to high degree of

double bond character of the peptide link (CONH) which results from the delocalization of nitrogen lone-pair of electrons on to the carbonyl group⁴. This observation in peptides gives an indication that delocalization of lone-pair of electrons from nitrogen, leads to the transfer of hydrogen to the formation of enol form. Thus, the deprotonation from nitrogen of amide which is unusual, takes place from oxygen via enol form.

The pK_a values of ligands and stability constants of the metal complexes are given in Table 1. pK_a values of these ligands follow the order : BTCMH > BTCH > BTCPH. The higher pK_a value of BTCMH is due to the presence of electron-donating methyl group, and lower pK_a in BTCPH is due to presence of electron-withdrawing phenyl group. The stability constant data reveal that 1 : 2 complexes are formed in all the systems. The comparison of stability of M(II)-BTCH/BTCMH/BTCPH implies that the substituent group on amine-N has significant effect on the formation of complexes in solution. The order of stabilities follow the sequence : M(II)-BTCMH > M(II)-BTCH > M(II)-BTCPH, which reflects the pK_a values of ligands. In all these ligands it has been observed that there is one dissociable proton and hence they are monobasic acid ligands. Though in these ligands number of donor sites is more, polynuclear complexes are not formed in presence of metal ions. Dissociation of amide proton from oxygen through enol form at lower pH in presence of metal ion, clearly indicates participation of oxygen in bonding.

TABLE 1—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANT DATA FOR M(II)-BTCH/BTCPH/BTCMH

Medium : 70% (v/v) DMF-water, temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.1 M

Ligand		Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Pb ^{II}
BTCH	log K ₁	7.50	6.26	6.20	6.09
	log K ₂	6.22	5.52	5.23	4.63
	log β ₂	13.72	11.78	11.43	10.72
BTCPH	log K ₁	5.79	4.95	5.34	5.50
	log K ₂	5.10	4.47	5.05	5.16
	log β ₂	10.89	9.42	10.39	10.66
BTCMH	log K ₁	7.25	6.74	6.95	8.02
	log K ₂	6.23	5.96	6.32	7.40
	log β ₂	13.48	12.70	13.27	15.42

Characterization of Cu^{II}-BTCH/BTCPPH/BTCMH complexes : Elemental analysis shows M-to-L ratio as 1 : 2. Physical and analytical data of the ligands and complexes are presented in Table 2. The absence of chloride indicates that chloride is neither present in coordination sphere nor outside. The ligands BTCH/BTCPPH/BTCMH have four possible donor sites, out of which two may be involved in bonding. From ir spectra of Cu^{II}-BTCH/BTCPPH/BTCMH, it is evident that the amide proton is lost on complexation. The ν_{NH} mode of amide group is observed in ligand at 2990 cm^{-1} , while in the complex the corresponding peak is not observed and an extra peak appears at 1620–1550 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$. From equilibrium studies it is evident that the complexation takes place through oxygen of amide group and either NH_2 group of hydrazide or S or N of benzothiazole. From ir spectrum it is evident that ν_{NH} of amide is absent. There is no considerable shift corresponding to NH_2 group, so participation of NH_2 is ruled out. Ir spectrum and TGA analysis reveal the absence of water molecule either in coordinated sphere or outside the sphere. The Cu^{II}-BTPPH/BTCMH showed the similar peaks.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF LIGANDS AND THE COMPLEXES*

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	μ_{eff} B.M.	Metal % : Found/ (Calcd.)
BTCH	Yellow	171	—	—
[Cu(BTCH) ₂]	Chocolate	DP	1.44	13.30 (14.10)
BTCPPH	Yellow	220	—	—
[Cu(BTCPPH) ₂]	Green	DP	1.75	11.60 (10.59)
BTCMH	Yellow	155	—	—
[Cu(BTCMH) ₂]	Chocolate	DP	2.05	14.51 (13.36)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

The absorption spectrum of Cu^{II}-BTCH shows four bands, which are assigned to transitions^{5,6} ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ (12738 cm^{-1}), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ (13262 cm^{-1}), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ (17761 cm^{-1}) and the band at 32894 cm^{-1} may be due to charge transfer band or ligand band^{7,8}. Cu^{II}-BTPPH and Cu^{II}-BTCMH complexes reveal only two transitions which are observed in visible region (12382, 22282 cm^{-1} and 12406, 22421 cm^{-1} respectively) indicating lesser separation between excited states (${}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{2g}$ and 2E_g). In Cu^{II}-BTCH complex, the observed magnetic moment (1.42 B.M.) indicates either distorted octahedral or square-planar geometry. The magnetic moments of Cu^{II}-BTPPH/-BTCMH are in expected range.

Epr spectrum of Cu^{II}-BTCH complex shows anisotropy in g values. The g_{\parallel} value at 2.392 and g_{\perp} value at 2.093 indicates tetragonal symmetry at metal ion⁹. From electronic absorption spectrum of Cu^{II}-BTCH also it is very clear that there are three $d-d$ transitions, which indicates well-separation of four energy states. In epr spectrum also the anisotropic g values can be explained through this supportive evidence from electron absorption spectrum.

In Cu^{II}-BTCMH and Cu^{II}-BTPPH complexes, the g values are isotropic. That means g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values are averaged to one value (2.1847 and 1.181)¹⁰. The absorption spectra of these complexes, where three peaks are expected, showed only two peaks. Though the geometry is square-planar, because of less energy separation between excited energy levels, only two peaks are observed in absorption spectra, which is again reflected in isotropic g values.

Hence it may be concluded that it is essential to calculate pK_a values of ligands and stability constants of complexes to get an understanding about various coordination sites of a ligand. Characterization of solid complexes which is based on analytical and various spectral data becomes more easy by having clear understanding of basicity and coordination tendencies of various coordination sites present in a ligand.

Experimental

The metal salts used were of A.R. grade. All the solvents used were purified¹¹. The metal ion solutions were standardized volumetrically¹². Carbonate-free KOH was standardized with potassium hydrogen phthalate. The experimental method consisted of potentiometric titration of the ligand in absence and presence of metal ion at 303 K and 0.1 M (KNO_3) ionic strength against standard KOH solution. The metal ions selected were Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II}.

Ligand BTCH was synthesized by the reported procedure¹³. A mixture of benzothiazole-2-ethyl carboxylate and phenylhydrazine/methylhydrazine in excess ethanol medium, was refluxed for 2–3 h and then cooled. The resulting solid BTPPH was washed with cold ethanol and crystallized as brownish yellow crystals, m.p. 220°. BTCMH was obtained as light yellow powder, m.p. 155°. The spectral data of the compounds are as follows : BTCH ν_{max} 3197 (CH arom), 1680 (C=O) 1618 (C=N), 3306, 2816 (NH_2), 2990 cm^{-1} (CONH), δ (EtOH- d_6 ; TMS) 4.8 (2H, br, NH_2), 7.6–7.8 (2H, m, ArH^a), 8.25 (2H, m, ArH^b), 10.5 (1H, br, NH), m/z 193 (77 M⁺), 162(31), 135(100) base peak, 108(31), 90(22), 82(22), 58(4), 45(4); BTPPH ν_{max} 3058 (CH arom), 1664 (C=O), 1601 (C=N), 3241 (CONH), 3317 (NH), δ (DMSO- d_6 ; TMS) 1.7 (2H, m, ArH^a), 8.25 (2H, m, ArH^b), 6.8 (3H, m, ArH^c), 7.2 (2H, t, ArH^d), 11.2 (1H, par br, NH), 8.1 (1H, s, phenyl NH), m/z 269(100), 162(22), 135(76), 90(28), 82(10), 77(74), 65(49), 58(6); BTCMH ν_{max} 3054 (CH arom), 1667 (C=O), 1556 (C=N), 2995 (CONH), 3314 (NH), δ (DMSO- d_6 ; TMS), 7.45 (2H, m, ArH^a), 7.9 (2H, m, ArH^b), 4.8 (1H, s, methyl NH), 10.2 (1H, s, amide NH), 2.65 (3H, s, CH_3), m/z 208(75), 191(4), 178(34), 162(24), 135(100), 109(9).

The complexes were synthesized by refluxing a mixture (pH 7) of the ligand (0.01 mol, dissolved in DMF and added to hot ethanolic solution) and aqueous solution of Cu-salt (0.005 mol) in 1 : 2 ratio. The separated solids were washed with ethanol followed by petroleum ether and dried under reduced pressure.

An Elico Li-120 pH-meter was used. pK_a values of ligands and stability constants of the corresponding complexes were calculated by Irving-Rossotti technique¹⁴ in 70% DMF-water medium. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by using a Faraday 7550 balance. Elemental analysis was carried out on Perkin-Elmer 240 C instrument. Chloride was estimated by Volhards method¹⁵. Metal was estimated by AAS on a Perkin-Elmer 2380 spectrometer. Conductivity was measured on a Degisum DI 909 conductivity bridge. Ir spectrum (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 435 spectrophotometer, far-ir spectra on a Shimadzu 1430 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu 106 spectrophotometer and epr spectra on a Joel SE 301 instrument (X band, low temp. -140°). M.ps. were recorded on a Toshniwal hot stage apparatus.

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